

WARPAGE BEHAVIOUR OF DISCONTINUOUS CF/PEEK THIN PLATES

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ABSTRACT

The use of discontinuous fibre composites has grown in the last decade due to advantages such as excellent formability, relatively isotropic properties, and potential for short processing times. However, there is still limited knowledge on the residual stress development of those composites and their resulting warpage behaviour. As the thickness of the composite plates is reduced, the warpage becomes more significant, creating a major processing challenge. The present work focuses on bringing a better understanding of the warpage behaviour of discontinuous thin plates, which supports current study on the prediction and modelling of this behaviour. Two different strand sizes were compared, small and large. For the small strands, an alignment grid was also proposed to better control the lay-up of the randomly oriented strands (ROS). Overall, the warpage of discontinuous CF/PEEK thin plates was found to decrease with the strand size in agreement with previous findings. The alignment grid showed favor the orientation of the strands at the 0° direction, 62% of the strands were found between -30° and +30°.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon-fibre reinforced thermoplastics have gained considerable attention as substitutes for various applications [1]. Discontinuous fibre composites, particularly long fibre reinforced thermoplastics, are spotlighted as an advanced material for lightweight design [2]. These discontinuous fibre composite materials have attracted increasing interest as promising alternatives to aluminium for applications [3,4]. In particular discontinuous carbon UD tape (i.e. strand) composites, which are usually processed by a compression moulding approach [4].

The discontinuous carbon fibre UD tape composites show advantages due to their balance between mechanical performance, formability, and manufacturing costs compared with continuous carbon fibre reinforced composites [1,3,4]. In addition, they exhibit a promising suitability for mass production and for the manufacture of complex geometrical structures [1,4].

However, several issues need to be considered during their application, as they usually show significant anisotropy and heterogeneity [3]. The random distribution of strands induces in-plane isotropic mechanical properties as well as a multi-scale structure and high heterogeneity, which make mechanical analysis of composites challenging [1].

Various aspects can impact in the part variability and need to be understood. The strands in-plane orientation is uncontrolled and varies from part-to-part, but also out-of-plane orientation is uncontrolled [5]. The cooling of thermoplastic composites from high melt temperatures (e.g. > 350°C) can induce residual stresses. Additionally, semi-crystalline thermoplastics such as polyether ether ketone (PEEK) have a fraction of the matrix that become more packed below the melting temperature, inducing matrix shrinkage and further residual stresses [6].

Selezneva and Lessard [7] observed an undesirable out-of-plane deflection, or warpage, as a prominent defect in carbon fibre/PEEK ROS plates. Collins [5] observed a high variability in the warpage shape when working with the same material. But there is still limited knowledge on the residual stress development of those composites as well as the influence of the strands' distribution and their resulting warpage behaviour.

Therefore, the objective of this work is to investigate the influence of strand size, orientation and distribution on the warpage of thin plates manufactured with chopped carbon fibre/PEEK UD tape.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

TenCate Cetex® TC1200 CF/PEEK UD tapes were used to manufacture 100 mm x 100 mm x 2mm plates. Two different strand sizes were compared maintaining the same aspect ratio, large strands and small strands, as shown in Table 1. For the large strands, a layup of $[0/90]_s$ was defined (Figure 1(a)). As it would not be practical to stack the small strands using the same layup, due to their diminutive size, they were distributed in the mould as randomly oriented strands (ROS). However, an alignment grid was also proposed in this work to better orient the small strands and minimize the user variability while distributing the strands inside the mould cavity.

Material type	Dimensions (mm)
Large strands	25.4 x 12.7
Small strands	6.4 x 3.2

Table 1: Discontinuous CF/PEEK strand sizes.

Figure 1: Alignment of (a) Large strands and (b) Small strands (with alignment grid).

2.2 Compression moulding cycle

The panels were manufactured in a 250 kN MTS load frame, retrofitted with a small instrumented hot press. A pressure of 10 bar was initially applied after which the mould was heated to 380°C. While maintaining a temperature of 380°C, the applied pressure was increased to 70 bar and allowed to dwell for 15 min. Finally, the part was cooled at a rate of approximately 10°C/min to room temperature maintaining a pressure of 70 bar throughout the cooling (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Process cycle for CF/PEEK composites.

2.3 Warpage measurement

A Faro ScanArm laser scanner was used to acquire surface position data for warpage computation. Two different approaches were considered and compared: 1) Effective flatness warpage and 2) Area weighted average warpage. The effective flatness measurement uses the data from the contour plots to compute the distance between the maximum and minimum points of the warped plate. Whereas the area weighted average warpage is computed by taking the volume between the warped surface and the zero-warpage plane and normalizing this value by the plate area, as shown in Figure 3. The volume above and below the zero-warpage plane was calculated separately and then added, and finally divided by the area of the plate.

Figure 3: Area weighted average warpage method [5].

2.4 Alignment grid

An experimental alignment grid was designed and built aiming to better orient the small strands and minimize the user variability while distributing the strands inside the mould cavity. The concept was inspired from the oriented strand board (OSB) industry and adapted to the small strands. The design proposed here consisted of a frame in which the alignment grid sits, as shown in Figure 4. The grid has a snug fit into the frame which allows it to be interchanged with different grid designs. The spacing of the lots is 3 mm. The parts were 3D printed with acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS) polymer using a fused deposition modeling (FDM) process.

Figure 4: Alignment grid. (a) Top view. (b) Isometric view.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Warpage measurement

The contour plots for the analyzed parts are depicted in Figure 5 while the values for the effective flatness warpage and area weighted average warpage are shown in Table 2. As it can be observed from the contour plots, the warped shape is consistent throughout the thin panels. There is a distinctive saddle-shape with two maxima and two minima along their free edges. However, a significant difference is verified in the magnitude of the warpage. Please note that the scale of the ‘out-of-plane distance’ from the small strands (ROS) panel is four times smaller than the others to provide a more accurate result.

The warpage decreased with the size of the strands as depicted in Table 2, indicating that the use of smaller strands can be beneficial to mitigate warpage. The observed behaviour can be explained by the fact that introducing discontinuities into the material changes the load transfer properties of the part, allowing the residual stresses created during cooling, due to shrinkage and coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) mismatch, to be better distributed. However, it is still not well understood if the small strands with a controlled lay-up would lead to less or more warpage compared with randomly oriented strands, as those conditions are yet to be compared.

Figure 5: Panel warpage contour plots for (a) Large strands and (c) Small strands (ROS).

Material Type	Effective Flatness Warpage (mm)	Area Weighted Average Warpage (mm)
Large strands	1.770 ± 0.127	0.235 ± 0.005
Small strands	0.730 ± 0.057	0.073 ± 0.004

Table 2: Warpage measurements.

3.2 Alignment grid

The efficacy of the alignment grid was tested at two different falling distances, 6.4 mm and 12.8 mm. Fifty small strands were used for each condition as shown in Figure 6. The orientation angle of the fallen strands was computed after they were manually passed through the alignment grid holes.

Figure 6. Orientation angles of the small strands (a) with grid at 6.4 mm, (b) with grid at 12.8 mm and (c) without grid at 12.8 mm.

Histograms of the small strands orientation angles are shown in Figure 7. At a height of 6.4 mm, a 0° orientation was favored; 62% of the strands were found between -30° and $+30^\circ$. As the falling distance increased to 12.8 mm, a more random distribution was observed, with only 38% of the strands oriented between -30° and $+30^\circ$. It was also verified that the grid could only contribute to the alignment of the strands at low heights (6.4 mm). At higher heights (12.8 mm), testes without the grid yielded similar random distribution of the orientation angles, as shown in Figure 7(c).

The normal distribution (bell curve) of the orientation angles for all conditions tested is depicted in Figure 8. The alignment grid showed to increase the probability of the small strands to stay within the angle range of -30° and $+30^\circ$ at a 6.4 mm falling height. As observed in the histogram, when the distance is doubled, the alignment effect is lost, having a similar behaviour as if no alignment grid was used. The optimum 6.4 mm falling height was found to be coincident with the small strands' length. Thus, in an ideal condition in which the strand falls in the longitudinal direction, when the strand leaves the grid, its opposite extremity is already in contact with the mould, favoring the alignment.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 7. Histogram of the small strands orientation angle at different falling distances: (a) with grid at 6.4 mm, (b) with grid at 12.8 mm and (c) without grid at 12.8 mm.

Figure 8. Normal distribution of the small strands' orientation angle at different falling heights.

3 CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions can be drawn from this study:

- The warpage of discontinuous CF/PEEK thin plates was found to decrease with the strand size, in agreement with previous findings. The use of small strands showed to be beneficial to mitigate warpage for the cases analyzed in this study.
- The small strands alignment grid showed to increase the occurrence of strands at the longitudinal direction, close to a 0° orientation. 62% of the strands were found between -30° and $+30^\circ$, against 38% without the grid. The optimum falling height, for the cases tested, was found to be coincident with the small strands length of 6.4 mm.
- The alignment grid shows to be a promising approach to better control the orientation of small strands. The influence of a more controlled lay-up in the warpage behavior of discontinuous CF/PEEK thin plates is still to be investigated.

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